

ISic0972

I.Sicily inscription 0972

Language

Ancient Greek

Type

funerary

Material

stone

Object**Editor**

Jonathan Prag

Principal Contributor

Jonathan Prag

Contributors

Jonathan Prag,James Cummings,James Chartrand,Valeria Vitale,Michael Metcalfe,Simona Stoyanova,Valentina Mignosa

Autopsy

No Autopsy

Last Change

2020-11-26 - Simona Stoyanova restructured bibliography

Place of origin (ancient)

Syracusae

Place of origin (modern)

Siracusa

Provenance

Catacomb of S.Giovanni

Coordinates**Current Location**

Italy, Sicily, Siracusa, Museo Archeologico
Regionale Paolo Orsi, inventory 93

Physical Description

Dimensions

Height cm

Width cm

Depth cm

Layout

Execution

Engraved

Letter Forms

Letter heights:

Line 1: mm

Interlineation

Interlineation line 1 to 2: mm

Text

1. ἐτελεύτηϛ
2. σεν · Μαρκιανὸς ·
3. μηνὶ Ὀκτωβρίῳ ·
4. κῆτε πυλῶνι
5. τρίτῳ · λανῶ
6. πένπητη σ ἐτῶν
7. λζ

Apparatus

Text of IG

Translation

Commentary

Digital identifiers:

TM 492597

EDCS 39102124

PHI 140448

Bibliography

Kaibel, G. 1890. Inscriptiones Graecae Siciliae et Italiae, additis graecis Galliae Hispaniae, Britanniae, Germaniae inscriptionibus. *Inscriptiones Graecae consilio et auctoritate Academiae Litterarum Regiae Borussicae Editae. Volumen XIV.* Berlin. At 14.0150 (<https://clio.columbia.edu/catalog/6873760>)

Boeckh, A., Franz, J., Curtius, E., Kirchhoff, A., Roehl, H. 1828-1887. Corpus Inscriptionum Graecarum. Berlin. At 4.9526

Agnello, S.L. 1953. Silloge di iscrizioni paleocristiane della Sicilia. Rome. At no.6

Consani, C. 1996. Koinai et Koiné dans la documentation épigraphique de l'Italie méridionale. In Brixhe, C.(eds.), *La Koiné grecque antique. II. La concurrence.* pp. 113-132. At 126

Licensed under a Creative

Commons-Attribution 4.0 licence.

Cite as:

J. Prag et al. (2020-12-17): ISic0972. <http://sicily.classics.ox.ac.uk>. (Collection: TEI edition). <http://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.4340228>